

Zybert Cosmology

Josef Zybert
ZybertCosmology@outlook.com

Abstract: Cosmology is in crisis! 95% of the universe is an unknown mysterious unidentified Dark Matter and Dark Energy. It has 40+ anomalies, inexplicable or inadequately explained. It is believed the Hubble Constant should have one value but accurate methods give two values. In 2020 this Hubble disparity reached 5σ . A crisis was declared. New physics was advocated. Herein, is a revolutionary new paradigm of the physical universe! A bold new physical model, which harmonizes the Hubble values, has no inherent anomalies and where the 40+ anomalies are inherent characteristic features. A model with no physical or mathematical abnormalities like singularities. A bold new model which explains 100% of the universe and is concordant with Classical Physics and Quantum Physics. A model named Zybert Cosmology.

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1 INTRODUCTION

My interest in neutron-antineutron gravitational interactions led to Cosmology and to conceiving Zybert Cosmology (ZC). ZC proclaims a bold new paradigm for the physical universe, a paradigm demanding a bold new vision of light and gravity, yet it uses Classical Physics and embraces Quantum Physics.

2 GENESIS

On 2018-01-19 while watching The Meaning of Life I thought that galaxies might be matter or antimatter. So I modelled this and to assess the models I set two Tests $H_0 \approx 7E4$ and $\rho \approx 1E-26$ at $T=13.8E9y$. Whether matter-antimatter repel is not known, so I postulated that matter-antimatter repel.

2.1 Instant Mass Creation

I simulated gravitational interactions between $M^+ = +6E42kg$ of neutrons (n) and $M^- = -6E42kg$ of antineutrons (\bar{n}). $\Delta V/\Delta R$, $\equiv H_0$, was 0 at $T=3y$ and other results clashed with observation. Now, when $V=U$ $\Delta V/\Delta R=0$, and, when $V \neq U$ $\Delta V/\Delta R \neq 0$, but, it demands a variable M. So, I analysed variable mass creation.

2.2 Variable Mass Creation

Simulations of numerous mass-time profiles showed potential. On 2018-03-08 17:52 using $R=1E-14$ and $M^\pm = \pm 1.67E-27$ at $T=4E-12s$ with $M=M*240$ and $T=T*10$ at each iteration, gave, at $T=14E9y$, $R=9.1E21$, $M=1.4E42$, $\Delta V/\Delta R/3E22=3.4E4$, and $3.4E5$ before and $3.4E3$ after, and $\rho=4.4E-25$, all in SI units, which will be used throughout.

Simulations were by spreadsheet and this one had 37 rows, yet, this simple rough simulation replicated a small ‘universe’ which nearly met the Tests. The same simulations which failed for instant mass creation for variable mass creation replicated a ‘universe’ with recognisable similarities to observation.

The implications were profound. Momentous. Historic.

2.3 A New Paradigm

Density variations in a new cloud of neutrons and antineutrons of growing mass can form a dominant cluster of antineutrons, which attracts antineutrons and repels neutrons, to evolve into a central antineutron sphere within a spherical neutron cloud where neutrons are repelled and accelerated radially outward.

This is a new type of entity in cosmology, and is now here named Zybertsphere, pronounced *zee-bet-sphere*, denoted \textcircled{Z} . \textcircled{Z} is also used as a prefix e.g. $\textcircled{Z}M$ to be read as Zybert mass. \textcircled{Z} can also be read as Zybertspheric e.g. \textcircled{Z} phenomena.

This is a new paradigm of the universe, a Zybert universe, as radically new and unique as Copernican Helio-centrism was to Ptolemaic Geo-centrism. An audacious bold new paradigm resolving Baryonic Asymmetry and Accelerating Expansion.

The above simulations also apply to test neutrons in \textcircled{Z} 's and test neutrons can represent entities, such as earth.

The spreadsheet was replaced with a computer program. One typical result, using $M=M*1.00048$ and $\Delta T=0.0001$ gave at $H_0=7E4$ $\textcircled{Z}M=2E298$, $\textcircled{Z}\rho=3.5E-26$ and $\textcircled{Z}T=17.2E9y$ and for earth $\textcircled{Z}R=5E107$, $\textcircled{Z}V=2E90$ and $\textcircled{Z}A=5E72$, in SI units.

Compared to this \textcircled{Z} , the observable universe is a miniscule insignificant little speck. The observable universe (or in ZC our visible sphere) is in our \textcircled{Z} , $Z\textcircled{Z}$. The $Z\textcircled{Z}$ centre is $Z\textcircled{Z}0$.

The results harmonized with measured data, and therefore, both matter-antimatter repulsion and variable mass creation forced themselves to be postulates of Zybert Cosmology.

Simulations identified the mass-time profile as crucial.

3 ZYBERT MASS EQUATION

Many simulations followed and most satisfied both Tests, if, mass increase started slowly then increased increasingly – which is an exponential form – and by using correct constants. But the age range at $H_0 \approx 7E4$ was enormous, $8.5E2:5.9E12y$. So, H_0 cannot designate age, because, $\Delta V/\Delta R$ is governed by $\Delta M/\Delta T$ which is defined by the mass-time profile.

It was unlikely mass increased forever so a sigmoidal form was chosen, Tanh, to replicate all possible mass-time profiles as the Zybert Mass Equation

$$M = Z_m * \text{Tanh} [T / Z_a - 1] + M_i \quad (1)$$

M & T are the log of ZM^- (or ZM^+) & ZT
 Z_m & Z_a set the inflexion point
 M_i sets the initial ZM (e.g. as $\pm 1.67E-27kg$)

4 ZYBERT ACCELERATION

The all-pervasive influence in Z 's is ZA . In M^+ Z 's ZA^- of the central ZM^- core and ZA^+ of the ZM^+ enveloping cloud, with ZA^- dominating over ZA^+ . Vice versa for M^- Z 's.

ZA acts along ZR , and forms the ultimate Z axis, centred at $Z0$, now named the Axis of Zybert $F(Z)$. Our $F(Z)$ is between earth and $Z(Z0)$. The Angle of Zybert $\theta(Z)$ is any angle to $F(Z)$.

Z 's are anisotropic and inhomogeneous, as is ZA and thus all motion. Motion in Z 's is absolute, relative to, fixed space and $Z0$ fixed in fixed space, so, both Cosmological Principles and some Equivalence Principles are irreconcilable with ZC.

4.1 Action of Zybert

ZA & A cause cosmic & local Z effects. Each is fundamental and hugely important, the now named Action of Zybert $\Lambda(Z)$. $\Lambda(Z) = \Lambda(Z)_{\text{cosmic}} + \Lambda(Z)_{\text{local}}$, each dominates its own region. $\Lambda(Z)_{\text{cosmic}} = \Delta(Z)A * \text{Cos}(\theta(Z))$ and $\Lambda(Z)_{\text{local}} = \Delta A * \text{Cos}(\theta)$ with $ZA = G * ZM^+ / ZR^2 + (ZR/R_0) * G * ZM^- / R_0^2$ $A = G * M / R^2$.

Locally $\Lambda(Z) \approx \Lambda(Z)_{\text{local}}$ and cosmically $\Lambda(Z) \approx \Lambda(Z)_{\text{cosmic}}$.

$\delta \Lambda(Z) / \delta ZR \equiv \Lambda(Z)'$ similarly for $\Lambda(Z)_{\text{c}}$ and $\Lambda(Z)_{\text{l}}$.

$\Lambda(Z)$ causes orbital precessions, velocity gains in flybys, constant rotation of galaxies, spacecraft deceleration, bending of light, increasing angular size of galaxies, GPS inaccuracy, anisotropy in c and H_0 , and so on.

4.1.1 Spacecraft Flybys

$\Lambda(Z)_{\text{c}}$ in the ecliptic plane is a centripetal acceleration to the sun. Using $V^2/R = \Lambda(Z)_{\text{l}} + \Lambda(Z)_{\text{c}}$ for the flyby of Galileo 1 past Earth at perigee, for $\Lambda(Z)_{\text{c}} = 1.01E-9m/s/s$ $V = V + 2.54mm/s$. $\Lambda(Z)_{\text{c}}$ to earth is $*4.3E-5$ to the sun. $\Lambda(Z)_{\text{c}}$ has a linked $\theta(Z)$. Because the ecliptic $\theta(Z) \neq 0$, $\Lambda(Z)_{\text{c}}$ varies from 0 to a maximum depending on the planet's orbital position at flyby.

4.1.2 Precession of Mercury

$\Lambda(Z)_{\text{c}}$ in Mercury's orbital plane is a centripetal acceleration. Using $V^2/R = \Lambda(Z)_{\text{l}} + \Lambda(Z)_{\text{c}} * \text{Cos}(\theta)$ along Mercury's orbit and iterating θ by 1° , a $\Lambda(Z)_{\text{c}} = 9.9272E-9m/s/s$ increases the orbit by $29073.46m = 5.02046E-7rad/88days$ or $42.98arcsec/100y$. This, and all, $\Lambda(Z)_{\text{c}}$'s have linked $\theta(Z)$'s.

4.1.3 Constant Rotation of Galaxies

$\Lambda(Z)_{\text{c}}$ in galactic planes is a centripetal acceleration. Using $V^2/R = \Lambda(Z)_{\text{l}} + \Lambda(Z)_{\text{c}} * R$ shows that above a certain R the galaxy rotation curve is 'flat' because as R increases $\Lambda(Z)_{\text{c}} * R$ compensates $\Lambda(Z)_{\text{l}}$. V vs R curves for M31, NGC 2366 and NGC 4157 were replicated precisely. Only one $\Lambda(Z)_{\text{c}}$ with one M vs R profile can reproduce each V vs R curve – this is Zybert TGM the ZC method to calculate Total Galactic Mass.

4.1.4 Increasing Angular Size of Galaxies

Angular sizes of galaxies, $\delta = d/D$, increase with D at higher D, due to a $\Lambda(Z)'$, where D at emission and at observation changes by $\Delta D = ut + (1/2)at^2$, where receding velocity $u = (D/3E22) * H_0$ and advancing acceleration $a = -\Lambda(Z)' * D$. At low D $ut > (1/2)at^2$ therefore D increases and δ decreases. At some D $ut = (1/2)at^2$ so δ is minimal. For higher D, a and t increase, so $ut < (1/2)at^2$ therefore D is lower than expected and δ increases.

4.2 Gradient of Zybert Acceleration

ZA' ($\delta ZA / \delta ZR$) is useful for small distances/durations, and it can be derived from observational data, possible, because, all $\Lambda(Z)$'s causing Z effects, like precession, can be calculated, and as each $\Lambda(Z)$ is a component of ZA ZA' can be derived from geometry. Analysing the geometry of s4.1.1 and s4.1.2 gave our local ZA' as $7.4426E-18m/s/s/m$. Thus for Mercury ($R = 5.79E10$) if $\theta(Z) = 98.735^\circ$ then $\Delta(Z)R = R * \text{Cos}(\theta(Z)) = 8.79E9$ and $\Lambda(Z) = ZA' * \Delta(Z)R * \text{Cos}(\theta(Z)) = 9.93E-9$ to give $42.98''/100y$. ZA' is now used as a third Test along with H_0 and ρ .

ZA is gravity, but gravity in ZC is somewhat different.

5 ZYBERT GRAVITY

Zybert Gravity is an extension of Newton Gravity.

In s2.2 $ZV = 2E90$, so gravity must act at $>2E90$, in effect instantaneously, in order for the central core to influence our visible sphere and create Z phenomena. Without ZA^- of the central ZM^- core H_0 would be 0 and there would be no actual physical cause for $H_0 \approx 7E4$. The observed data demands that the instantaneous action of gravity must be a postulate of ZC.

Corollaries of the ZC matter-antimatter postulate are that antigravity is coupled to antimatter as gravity is to matter.

Zybert Gravity is coupled to mass and light equally, each is accelerated by and accelerates by GM/R^2 .

$ZA \gg A$ but locally $ZA' < A'$ and $ZA' > A'$ cosmically.

Somewhat related is the speculative postulate that for each $n-\bar{n}$ pair $\Sigma E = 0$ and therefore that for each Z $\Sigma E = 0$.

6 ZYBERT LIGHT

Zybert Light is an extension of Newton Light.

In s2.2 $\mathbb{Z}V=2E90$, but, we observe light gets to targets in straight lines at $3E8$. Locally, source and target move at $\mathbb{Z}V$, due to $\mathbb{Z}A$, therefore light when emitted must also have the same $\mathbb{Z}V$, in addition to c , otherwise light would not get to local targets in straight lines at c . The absolute speed of light relative to fixed space and relative to $\mathbb{Z}0$ fixed in fixed space, is its Zybert speed, denoted by \mathbb{C} , whereas c is its Eigen speed. $\Lambda\mathbb{Z}$ (cosmic and local) also changes \mathbb{C} .

Zybert Light has no inherent contradictions, is not counter-intuitive, does not beggar belief, does not lead to paradoxes, explains many cosmological phenomena, resolves anomalies, and, is concordant with Classical and Quantum Physics.

Hence, a variable speed of light, additive with the source, demand to be postulates of Zybert Cosmology.

6.1 Relative Speed of light

The speed of light relative to an observer is $\hat{c}=\mathbb{C}-\mathbb{Z}V$. This is observed as a change in v or λ , now known as Zybertshift $\mathbb{Z}z$. \hat{c} can be $<$ or $=$ or $>$ c or 0 . In the lab $\hat{c} \approx c$ but usually $\hat{c} \neq c$, mainly because there is always a $\Lambda\mathbb{Z}$, no matter how small.

6.2 Zybertshift

$\mathbb{Z}z$ is defined as \hat{c}/c , or some equivalent such as v_o/v_e or E_o/E_e . UnterZybertshift ${}^u\mathbb{Z}z$ is $\hat{c}<c$ and uberZybertshift ${}^u\mathbb{Z}z$ is $\hat{c}>c$.

The Doppler Effect is for sound where λ actually changes, but it is inapplicable to light where velocity actually changes, now named the Zybert Effect to differentiate the two.

$\mathbb{Z}z$ is evaluated with Kinematics iterated along a light path to account for $\Lambda\mathbb{Z}$ (cosmic and local) and \hat{c} at emission.

6.2.1 Zybertshift.local

$\mathbb{Z}z$.local is due to a $\Lambda\mathbb{Z}$.local acting along the light path which alters \mathbb{C} , and \hat{c} . So, Sag-A* (8.26E36kg) slows light to $\mathbb{Z}z=0$ at 220m, PSR J0348+0432 (4.0E30kg) to 0.735 at 1.05E7m and earth (6E24kg) to $\mathbb{Z}z=0.9999999993$ at 1.0E12m, or just 0.21m/s in 3E8m/s. This is miniscule, but, GPS corrections must offset local uberZybertshift ${}^u\mathbb{Z}z$.local by earth, ${}^u\mathbb{Z}z$.earth.

6.2.2 GPS Correction

GPS $V=3844.544$ m/s in orbits at an altitude of 20197267.2m. With $c=299792458$ m/s, Emitter \hat{c} as $\hat{c}.E$, Receiver \hat{c} as $\hat{c}.R$ and ${}^u\mathbb{Z}z$.earth from E to R $\Delta c=+0.158640027$ m/s ($\Delta t \approx 67.4$ ms)

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{c}.E &= \sqrt{(c^2+V^2)} = 299792458.024651 \text{ and} \\ \hat{c}.R &= \sqrt{((c+\Delta c)^2+V^2)} = 299792458.183291 \text{ and so} \\ \Delta \hat{c} &= \hat{c}.R - \hat{c}.E = +0.158640027, \text{ and to offset this} \\ \hat{c}.E &= \hat{c}.E - \Delta \hat{c} = 299792457.866011 \text{ and so} \\ \mathbb{Z}z &= \hat{c}.E/c = 0.999999999553062. \end{aligned}$$

For GPS receivers to receive $v.R$ of 10.23Mhz
 $v.E$ must be offset to $10.23 * \mathbb{Z}z$ or 10.2299999954278.
 GPS atomic clock L-band v is set to 10.22999999543.

6.2.3 Zybertshift.cosmic

$\mathbb{Z}z$.cosmic is due to a $\Lambda\mathbb{Z}$.cosmic along the light path which alters \mathbb{C} , and \hat{c} . $\Lambda\mathbb{Z}=\Delta\mathbb{Z}A*\text{Cos}(\theta\mathbb{Z})$ causes anisotropy in \mathbb{C} and as $\mathbb{Z}M \propto \mathbb{Z}T$ so too $\mathbb{Z}A \propto \mathbb{Z}T$, but how measurements of the Fine Structure Constant are affected was not analysed.

6.3 Zybertrefraction

Zybertshift is a change in light speed and Zybertrefraction is a change in direction, defined as the relative instantaneous angle $\mathbb{Z}\theta$ of light at any point in the light path. Zybertrefraction $\mathbb{Z}\theta$ also causes Zybertshift $\mathbb{Z}z$. $\mathbb{Z}\theta$ is highest and $\mathbb{Z}z$ is lowest for \mathbb{Z} circumferential light paths and vice versa for radial paths. Both $\mathbb{Z}z$ and $\mathbb{Z}\theta$ are reflected in vector \mathbb{C} .

6.3.1 Zybertrefraction.local

$\mathbb{Z}\theta$.local is from a $\Lambda\mathbb{Z}$.local transverse to the light path due to local mass M^+ ($A^+>0$) or M^- ($A^-<0$).

6.3.2 Zybertrefraction.cosmic

$\mathbb{Z}\theta$.cosmic is from a transverse $\Lambda\mathbb{Z}$.cosmic. Geometric angle $\Delta y/\Delta x$ is less than the instantaneous angle $\delta y/\delta x$ ($\mathbb{Z}\theta$.cosmic), this is an inherent feature of the curvature of motion in \mathbb{Z} 's. $\delta y/\delta x$ is $\mathbb{Z}\theta$.cosmic and $\Delta y/\Delta x$ is the physical geometry.

6.3.3 Bending of Light from Hyades (1919)

$\mathbb{Z}\theta$.local + $\mathbb{Z}\theta$.cosmic is bending of light.

Iterating $\Lambda\mathbb{Z}$.local, $\Delta(GM/R^2)*\text{Cos}(\theta)$, along a light path grazing the sun ($M=2E30$ $R=7E8$) has $\mathbb{Z}\theta$.local=0.875", equal to Newton's $2*G*M/(R*c^2)$. Hyades is 1.45E18m away and light to our sun takes 1.53E2y. With Hyades at 0,0, the Sun at +1° to the x-axis and $\Lambda\mathbb{Z}$ 'cosmic=3.469907019E-19m/s/s/m along the y-axis, for light rays a and b from Hyades at -12.895° and -12.895236° at the sun $\delta y/\delta x=0.234557314$ rad $y=-7.0E8$ m and $\delta y/\delta x=0.2345615559$ rad $y=+1.23E11$ m, on curved paths, and the $\delta y/\delta x$ difference is 4.24E-6rad, 0.87", where ray b is observed at a point 5 months before the eclipse. Light bending is $\mathbb{Z}\theta$.local=0.875" by the sun + $\mathbb{Z}\theta$.cosmic=0.87" between the January and May 1919 light rays due to $\Lambda\mathbb{Z}$.cosmic from Hyades to the sun – combined to give the Zybert value 1.75".

$\mathbb{Z}\theta$.cosmic from the sun to the earth, in this short distance, is small compared to both $\mathbb{Z}\theta$.local by the sun and $\mathbb{Z}\theta$.cosmic from Hyades to the sun. Per metre, $\mathbb{Z}\theta$.cosmic \ll $\mathbb{Z}\theta$.local.

Galaxies and galaxy clusters can refract light from galaxies perceived as full or parts of annuli encircling the refractors.

6.4 Eigen Energy of Light

Zybert Light preserves its Eigen v and λ and E . Any perceived changes are due to \hat{c} thus $E=pc=hv$ and $\delta E=p(\hat{c}-c)=p\delta c=h\delta v$, and $E+\delta E$ is observed, such as by sensors. 1.022MeV photons unterZybertshifted to 1.000MeV can convert to $e-\bar{e}$ pairs, but, 1.000MeV photons uberZybertshifted to 1.022MeV cannot.

7 ZYBERT TIME

Time in Zybert Cosmology, Zybert Time, is fully concordant with Newtonian Mechanics and Quantum Mechanics.

8 ZYBERT SIMULATION MODEL

The constants used are neutron $M=1.67E-27$ & $R=5E-16$ and $G=6.667408E-11$, in SI, and the equations used are

$$\begin{aligned}
 M &= Z_m * \tanh [T / Z_a - 1] + M_i \\
 T &= T + \Delta T \\
 \textcircled{A}^- &= G * \textcircled{M}^- / \textcircled{R}^2 \text{ for the central core} \\
 \textcircled{A}^+ &= \textcircled{R} * G * \textcircled{M}^+ / R_o^3 \text{ for the enveloping cloud} \\
 \textcircled{A} &= (\textcircled{A}^- + \textcircled{A}^+) * IC \\
 \textcircled{V} &= \textcircled{U} + \textcircled{A} * \textcircled{T} \\
 \textcircled{R} &= \textcircled{U} * \textcircled{T} + (1/2) * \textcircled{A} * \textcircled{T}^2 \\
 \textcircled{\rho} &= \textcircled{M} / ((4/3) * \pi * \textcircled{R}^3) \text{ in early simulations} \\
 \textcircled{Z} &= \Delta \textcircled{V} / \Delta \textcircled{R} / 3.086E22 \\
 M &= \log(\textcircled{M}^- \text{ or } \textcircled{M}^+) \text{ \& } T = \log(\textcircled{T}) \\
 R_o &\text{ is the neutron cloud outer radius} \\
 IC &\text{ parameterizes } \textcircled{A} \text{ so simulations reproduce } \textcircled{A}'
 \end{aligned}$$

Results of simulations for $\Delta T=E-3:E-6$ showed that all \textcircled{Z} parameters were asymptotic third order polynomials of $R^2=1$. $\Delta T=E-4$ was a good speed/accuracy compromise. It is useful to extrapolate quick $\Delta T \geq E-5$ results to get the more accurate $\Delta T \leq E-6$ results without lengthy $\Delta T \leq E-6$ simulations.

Z_m and Z_a set the \textcircled{M} vs \textcircled{T} inflexion point; physically, Z_m governs the final \textcircled{M} and Z_a influences \textcircled{Z} and age \textcircled{T} , and they determine the nature of the resulting \textcircled{Z} .

The simulation model consistently yielded $\textcircled{A}' \sim E-35$ not the derived $7.44E-18$. To increase \textcircled{A}' \textcircled{R} had to be reduced. I chose parameterization by setting $\textcircled{A}=\textcircled{A}'*IC$. In doing so, \textcircled{Z} , \textcircled{Z}' , $\textcircled{\rho}$ and \textcircled{M} & \textcircled{T} were unaffected, but IC vs \textcircled{A}' had a linear correlation of $R^2=1$. I later discovered the physical interpretation of IC is that the radial density profile of \textcircled{M}^+ is weighted toward the core. Hence, $\textcircled{\rho}$ had to be calculated using, the \textcircled{M}^+ and the volume, between two test neutrons. Note that IC is an average value since radial density profiles were not part of current simulations.

The neutron-antineutron creation process is adjacent the core surface at the matter-antimatter interface, so \textcircled{R} & \textcircled{V} of neutrons at creation are set to \textcircled{R} & \textcircled{V} of the core surface. All motion in \textcircled{Z} 's is absolute, relative to both fixed space and \textcircled{Z} centres which are fixed in fixed space.

Outside the neutron cloud $\textcircled{A}=0$ and $\Delta \textcircled{V}=0$ so the two lead test neutrons have an oscillatory motion as each overtakes the other, but this was avoided by setting $R_o=2*\textcircled{R}$ and the latest simulations use two or more test neutrons.

Calculation precision was set to 1024 digits since machine precision of desktop PC's of 15 digits is often insufficient.

By these refinements of the simulation model, many more simulations allowed a better understanding of the character of the evolution of \textcircled{Z} 's.

$Z_m=E2:E6$ replicate \textcircled{Z} 's which could be our \textcircled{Z} , $Z_m > E6$ might but these were not fully analysed. $Z_m=0.25E3:512E3$ seem most viable to replicate our \textcircled{Z} .

Remarkably, the Zybert Mass Equation always replicated \textcircled{Z} 's which met all three Tests.

9 ZYBERTSPHERE CHARACTERISTICS

Ever more simulations revealed or confirmed many inherent fascinating characteristic features of Zybertspheres.

9.1 Baryonic Symmetry

All \textcircled{Z} 's form from newly created neutron-antineutron pairs and the increase in \textcircled{M} is given by the Zybert Mass Equation. Almost all antineutrons in $Z\textcircled{Z}$ are in the central $Z\textcircled{M}^-$ core.

9.2 Zybert Expansion

$\textcircled{Z}X$ is Absolute Zybert Expansion outward from $\textcircled{Z}0$, $\Delta \textcircled{Z}X$ is Relative Zybert Expansion ($\textcircled{Z}X.2-\textcircled{Z}X.1$) and $\Delta \textcircled{Z}X/\Delta \textcircled{R}$ is Normalised Relative Zybert Expansion - the Zybert Parameter $\textcircled{Z}Z$ - a fundamental parameter in Zybert Cosmology which is the counterpart of H_0 . $\textcircled{Z}Z$ vs \textcircled{T} is log-log linear with $R^2=1$ and $\delta \textcircled{Z}Z(t)/\delta t$ is denoted $\textcircled{Z}Z'$, *zee-bet-zee-dot*.

$\textcircled{Z}X$ cannot be measured directly but it can be derived. Its manifestation $\textcircled{Z}Z$ can be measured, and has been as H_0 .

In ZC $\textcircled{Z}Z$ is generally higher in the past, thus $\textcircled{Z}Z$ at 2Mpc is higher than twice at 1Mpc and $\textcircled{Z}Z$ vs \textcircled{T} is log-log linear. But note, $\textcircled{Z}Z$ vs \textcircled{T} for neutrons created at higher \textcircled{T} 's have a more complex profile, initially.

$\Delta \textcircled{Z}X$ also occurs within e.g. galaxies and planetaries, but is swamped by $\Lambda \textcircled{Z}.local$. No simulations were done to check if opposing expansive $\Delta \textcircled{Z}X$ vs contractive $\Lambda \textcircled{Z}.local$ affects e.g. the net change in AU (Astronomical Unit).

9.2.1 Anisotropy in the Zybert Parameter

Simulations using $Z_m=0.25E3:512E3$ all met the three Tests, so, Z_m of our \textcircled{Z} was not identified. But simulation results did hint that \textcircled{Z} anisotropy might identify Z_m . Specifically, the anisotropy of $\textcircled{Z}Z$ which has a correlation with \textcircled{M} .

Simulating motions of earth and EMR from X-ray sources at $r=217Mpc$ from earth, at $\theta \textcircled{Z}=0^0$ and $\theta \textcircled{Z}=90^0$, using

$$\begin{aligned}
 \textcircled{Z}R.x &= \textcircled{Z}R.e - r \\
 \textcircled{Z}V.x &= \textcircled{Z}V.e - H_0 * r + c
 \end{aligned}$$

where .e is the earth and

.x is the X-ray source

using the ZC Simulation Model equations and the iteration interval $r/10000$

showed a $\textcircled{Z}Z$ anisotropic disparity of 4701 for $Z_m=0.25E3$ and 4697 for $Z_m=512E3$, $4/7E4$ or 0.006%, which should be measurable. Other anisotropies or $\Delta \textcircled{Z}Z/\Delta \textcircled{R}$ or $\Delta \textcircled{A}'/\Delta \textcircled{R}$ also might help identify our unique Z_m .

9.3 Zybertzone

A fundamental feature of \textcircled{Z} 's was revealed when simulations showed that neutrons created up to $\textcircled{Z}=7E4$ had similar $\textcircled{Z}R$, therefore defining three zones – at $\textcircled{Z}R$, at $<\textcircled{Z}R$ and at $>\textcircled{Z}R$. In the $<\textcircled{Z}R$ zone new neutrons stream outward and $\textcircled{Z}\rho$ drops from $\sim E9$ near the core to $\sim E-26$ at $\textcircled{Z}R$. In the $>\textcircled{Z}R$ zone $\textcircled{Z}\rho$ drops from $\sim E-26$ at $\textcircled{Z}R$ to 0 at R_o . The $\textcircled{Z}R$ zone is unique. This zone is named the Zybertzone, $\textcircled{Z}zz$.

Using multiple test neutrons shows the Zybertzone to be a thin spherical annulus within the neutron sphere, which grows yet maintains its integrity. This zone is characteristic of the morphology of spherical \textcircled{Z} 's and it satisfies all three Tests. It is not a sharply defined zone, rather, it is a radial region where $\textcircled{Z}\rho$ is $\sim E-26$, between $\sim E9$ at the core surface and 0 at R_o .

Zybertzone constituents are neutrons, protons, electrons, light nuclei, photons and some anti-equivalents.

Initially, they accelerate outward in a starburst firework formation, and then newer baryons reach the Zybertzone inner surface, with a higher $\textcircled{Z}V$ under a higher $\textcircled{Z}A^-$ and enter the Zybertzone, thus mixing the older and newer constituents.

This zone is a thin active 'atmosphere', like on the sun, or earth where life forms, but in \textcircled{Z} 's stars form. The Zybertzone is an active zone, where densities and time scales produce conditions conducive to star formation through gravity. The term stelliferous applies to Zybertzones.

The formation of Zybertzones in \textcircled{Z} 's seem an inevitable evolutionary outcome, as though gravitational dynamics move neutrons created during a 'Goldilocks time' to all merge into a 'Goldilocks zone', a spherical annulus, the Zybertzone. This is a typical evolutionary path for \textcircled{Z} 's having $\textcircled{Z}Z\sim 7E4$, and virtually all do so. A path which always creates a Zybertzone.

Our visible sphere is within the Zybertzone of our \textcircled{Z} .

9.4 Zybertwind

Stars produce an outbound wind of H plasma, and so do \textcircled{Z} 's. But with \textcircled{Z} 's the plasma has a different origin. In the turbulent creation zone at the matter-antimatter interface, newly created neutrons decay and combine and re-combine into protons, electrons, light nuclei, photons etc. along with some anti-equivalents from entrapped antineutrons which decay into antiprotons-antielectrons or combine with neutrons as photons and all stream out from the neutron-antineutron creation zone to form the now named Zybertwind.

Zybertwind is like Solar Wind and Solar Flares, except, newly created neutrons stream out from the core due to $\textcircled{Z}A^-$, but similarly, in the magnetic field of the central $\textcircled{Z}M^-$ core as chaotic \textcircled{Z} flares within a continuous stream.

9.4.1 Inverse Compton Scattering

Inverse Compton Scattering (ICS) between, Zybertwind and Zybertzone plasmas, increases downwind velocity of photons, which distorts Zybertshift of light, and collisions increase the downwind velocity of mass. ICS also creates other \textcircled{Z} effects.

9.4.2 Zybert Microwave Environment

Zybertwind plasma interacts with Zybertzone plasma, which emits Blackbody Bremsstrahlung microwaves now known as Zybert Microwave Radiation ZMR, and all the superimposed unterZybertshifted individual ZMR in all directions is all sky microwave EMR – the Zybert Microwave Environment ZME, and manifestly correlates with the cosmic distribution of mass. 290Ghz ZMR at 2E3Mpc ($\textcircled{Z}z=0.55$) or ZME within 4E3Mpc, if using sensors of $> 30\text{Ghz}$, is measured as Blackbody EMR peaking at 160Ghz, equivalent to a Blackbody at 2.725K, but, ZME is unrelated to a cosmic temperature.

9.5 Cosmic Rays & UHECR

The protons/electrons/nuclei, with a tiny proportion being the entrapped anti-equivalents, all as components of Zybertwind reach our visible sphere and us as Cosmic Rays and UHECR. Their enormous original energies dissipate, through collisions and Bremsstrahlung radiation in traversing the Zybertzone, down to up to $E21eV$ as they pass earth.

The highest Cosmic Ray energy is $\sim E21eV$. A neutron at $U=4.4E14m/s$ has $KE=(1/2)*M*U^2 = E21eV$. $\textcircled{Z}U=U+\textcircled{Z}V$ and Earth has an outward radial $\textcircled{Z}V\approx E28m/s$.

Cosmic Rays are part of Zybertwind, and Zybertwind increases downwind velocity of ZME, creating a ZME dipole, and the uberZybertshifted ZME direction, viewed as a dipole, correlates with the UHECR source direction.

Cosmic Rays originate from a particular direction, which is more apparent from UHECR, and this direction is $Z\textcircled{Z}0$, which is along the Axis of Zybert, and therefore there should be a correlation between the Cosmic Ray direction dipole and various large-scale anisotropies.

9.6 Neutron Spheres

Neutron Spheres (NS) are formed either from newly created neutrons repelled from the \textcircled{Z} core, or, remnants of stars.

As a \textcircled{Z} evolves, newly created neutrons envelop the core and are repelled. In this dense chaotic turbulent cloud, random density variations create neutron clusters before free neutrons start decaying into protons-electrons.

As $\textcircled{Z}A^-$ repels the cloud, in a form like solar flares within a continuous stream, radial expansion separates the clusters and subsequently, other clusters and newer free neutrons or groups of neutrons may merge with and enlarge them.

A neutron at $1E-15m$ has $A^+=+1.1146E-7m/s/s$. Near the surface of a NS (M^+ or M^-) of any mass in the same $1E-15m$ $\Delta A^+\approx\pm 2.4E-7m/s/s$. Therefore, two or more adjacent neutrons near the central $Z\textcircled{Z}M^-$ core have $A^+ = \geq +1.11E-7 + \leq +2.4E-7$ and both tend to maintain cluster integrity in the enveloping, expanding, radially outwardly accelerating neutron cloud.

While clusters are repelled from the core, $\Lambda\textcircled{Z}$ coalesces them into NS's. A full analysis of NS formation needs a full simulation but a basic analysis can demonstrate the principle.

Simulations of \textcircled{Z} 's give $\textcircled{Z}Z$ vs $\textcircled{Z}T$ during their evolution.

Using $V=U+A*T$, a receding $U=(Z/R/3E22)$ is offset by an advancing $A*T$ where $A=GM^+/R^2$ of local mass. Initially, $U \gg A*T$ so local baryons are receding, but, U is decreasing because Z is decreasing, and when $U=A*T$ $V=0$ and local baryons stop receding, and as U decreases further A dominates and the local baryons start collapsing.

Initially, $Z > E22$ and $\rho > E9$ and an $M=3E34$ within $R=3E9$ reaches $V=0$ at $T \approx 160s$ and those neutrons slowly start to coalesce, which generally initiates at neutron clusters which had previously formed, to form NS's of varying masses which could be up to billions of solar masses. These are the first multi-baryon entities to form in $(M^+) Z$'s. But neutrons created later start with a more complex Z vs T profile.

Simulating unterZybertshift of an $M=8E40kg$ $R=3.53E7m$ NS shows light stops in $7E-8s$ at $10m$ altitude, and for Sag-A* of $M=8.26E36kg$ $R=1.65E6m$ light stops in $1.5E-6s$ at $220m$. The smallest NS to stop light is $\sim 1.3E31kg$ - a Zybertdwarf. Escape velocity $\sqrt{2GM/R}$ gives $\sim 1.3E31kg$. In ZC , Sag-A*, and at the centre of almost all galaxies, is a Neutron Sphere.

9.7 Galaxy Formation

A detailed explanation of galaxy formation in ZC needs better simulations than have been done so far, but some analyses can provide guidance.

Generally, galaxies form around NS's after they and their surrounding local sea of baryons are repelled from the core. NS's form at $T < E6s$ in dense clouds near the core before the newly created neutrons start decaying into protons-electrons.

Typically, initially, $Z > E22$ and the receding $V \gg 0$ and as the Zybertzone expands Z and ρ fall. After some time, perhaps a long time, when local gravity of NS's nullifies Z , $V=0$ and local baryons start collapsing to form proto galaxies, mainly around NS's since their gravity forms focal points, even though NS's had formed much (much) earlier.

NS gravity attracts surrounding baryons, proportionally, but, subject to the density profile of surrounding baryons and accretion of near-by mass, NS's may have less bound baryons resulting in varying ratios of Total Galactic Mass to NS Mass. Baryon clouds may have no, or only small, NS's but can still evolve into clusters of stars. All these are proto galaxies, and ΛZ (local & cosmic) may cause proto galaxies to merge and create larger ones (proto galaxies and NS's) which then attract and merge with others nearby, or, proto galaxies are disrupted and may re-form or collide with others nearby.

ΛZ .local of the central NS results in baryon density being higher closer to the galaxy centre and decreases outward.

The baryon clouds of proto galaxies produce stars (and planets and so on), perhaps seeded by nano NS's, to become active galaxies, and, for most stars after their fuel is spent they will form Stellar Neutron Spheres (SNS), which are the same but smaller than, Galactic Neutron Spheres (GNS).

This continues and it forms the evolving Zybertzone, and within which in Z is our visible sphere, where some stars are still visible from that era, e.g. BD +17° 3248 and HD 140283.

9.8 Age of Stars

The oldest stars are BD +17° 3248 $13.8 \pm 4E9y$ and HD 140283 $14.5 \pm 0.8E9y$ – an extremely metal-deficient 7th-magnitude spectral class F3 sub-giant now just out of the main sequence. With a mass of $\sim 0.8M_{\odot}$ it should be main-sequence for up to $21E9y$. Thus, as one of the first Population II stars, it sets the start of star formation in our visible sphere at $\sim 20E9y$ ago.

Hence, in Z , it was $>20E9y$ ago that clouds of baryons ceased expanding and began collapsing, to form the first stars, the Population III stars, being massive stars that lived for a few million years, went supernova and created heavier elements. These early super-massive stars were effectively mini proto galaxies, which were able to collapse readily, possibly with nano NS's acting as seeds. Thus, it is expected there are few metal-poor stars left by now, but with a high metal abundance of hot x-ray-emitting intergalactic gas in clusters of galaxies.

9.9 Origin of Voids

In the choppy turbulent chaotic creation zone at the matter-antimatter interface, antineutrons become entrapped within the neutron layer and as this layer is repelled from and by the central core so too are the entrapped antineutrons.

Some collide with neutrons to form photons. The surviving antineutrons create entrapped antineutron spheres which repel the surrounding local neutrons thus creating spherical voids producing Swiss-cheese or bubble-bath type structures within the broader neutron cloud and also within very large structures when and if they are formed as part of Zybertspheric flares.

The Zybertzone expands outward, density decreases, voids enlarge and two or three abut, creating filamentary and sheet or globular structures of baryons between the abutting voids.

Voids are smaller in higher density regions from the higher local A^+ of baryons surrounding the void, and sphericity varies with surrounding baryon distribution and local baryon flow.

As voids grow, baryons nearer the centre are increasingly repelled to the periphery, and this accumulation of baryons creates a denser spherical annulus around the periphery. ZMR creation here will be higher due to the higher mass interacting with Zybertwind. Because the line of sight through a periphery has a higher mass than through the body, there is also higher ZMR, which creates ring structures in the ZME, some of which may be visible from earth.

Contrarily, since voids are devoid of mass, any line of sight which includes a void has a lower mass therefore less ZMR, which will be observed as a darker region in the ZME.

The correlation of the ZME with these structures and other masses is reduced since the ZME is a superposition of ZMR from varying ZT 's and ZR 's of an expanding Zybertzone.

9.9.1 Antineutron Sphere at Centre of Bootes Void

If Bootes void has $R=1.56E24m$, an antineutron sphere of M^- , with baryons within R^*E4m , of gaseous density $4E-21$, attains gravitational equilibrium when $M^- = -4E36kg$ i.e. $-2E6M_{\odot}$. Large by SNS standards but small by GNS standards.

9.9.2 Baryons within Voids

Baryons and baryonic galaxies may be found within voids but it is unlikely there are any anti-baryonic galaxies within voids. In $Z(\otimes)$, if repulsive $M^- \Lambda(\otimes).local = attractive \Lambda(\otimes)'.cosmic * R$, then baryonic entities have relative gravitational stability.

9.10 Variation of Fundamental Constants

Two fundamental constants are used in ZC, neutron mass M and the Gravitational Constant G. Simulations using $M=M*2$ and $M/2$ and $G=G*2$ and $G/2$ showed that $\otimes Z$, $\otimes \dot{Z}$, $\otimes A'$ and $\otimes T$ were unchanged, $\otimes \rho$ was changed by G but not by M and other parameters like $\otimes R$ and $\otimes V$ changed by $*1.25$ or $/1.25$, but otherwise Zybertspheres were unchanged.

9.11 Zybert Golden Correlations

\otimes 's, as individual during evolution or multiple at $\otimes Z=7E4$, have linear log-log correlations of \otimes parameters (21 multiple are non-linear), all mostly with $R^2 = 1$ or ≈ 1 , for example

$$\begin{aligned} \otimes T &= -1.0008 * \otimes \dot{Z} + 4.8372 & R^2 &= 1 \\ \otimes R &= 0.3333 * \otimes M + 2.3991 & R^2 &= 1 \\ Z_a &= 0.048 * Z_m + 22.851 & R^2 &= 1 \\ \Delta \otimes A' / \Delta \otimes T &= 1.0003 * \otimes \dot{Z} - 21.67 & R^2 &= 1 \end{aligned}$$

The following correlations are common to both individual \otimes 's during growth and multiple \otimes 's at $\otimes Z=7E4$, with $R^2 = 1$ (again, \otimes parameters are logarithms).

$$\begin{aligned} \otimes T & \text{ vs } \otimes Z, \otimes \dot{Z} \\ \otimes M & \text{ vs } \otimes R, \otimes V, \otimes A, \Delta \otimes A' / \Delta \otimes R \\ \otimes R & \text{ vs } \otimes M, \otimes V, \otimes A, \Delta \otimes A' / \Delta \otimes R \\ \Delta \otimes Z / \Delta \otimes R & \text{ vs } \otimes M, \otimes V, \otimes A, \otimes R, \Delta \otimes A' / \Delta \otimes R \end{aligned}$$

This nature of \otimes 's is surprising and a great revelation. That \otimes 's have such an orderly evolution, and produce fundamental properties like $\otimes Z$, $\otimes \dot{Z}$, $\otimes A'$ and $\otimes \rho$, which are measurable, and which are so simply interrelated and so highly correlated. A fascinating and appealing quality reflecting a symmetry of \otimes 's where correlations of most parameters are linear and most with $R^2 = 1$ or ≈ 1 .

A natural system which has such complexity yet an innate mathematical simplicity and elegance, which can be simulated by a few simple well known trusted equations, and postulates which forced themselves into ZC based on observations.

9.12 Unification

A profound consequence of the Zybert Cosmology paradigm is that Zybert Time, Zybert Light and Zybert Gravity, easily formalises and unifies hitherto unrelated phenomena while simultaneously resolving current anomalies and the anomalies resolved herein confirm that those anomalies are inherently natural characteristic features of Zybertspheres.

10 HUBBLE CRISIS

The two principal methods giving H_0 are Type 1a supernovae as $71.5E3:74E3$ for $z=0.4:0.6$ and ESA-Planck as $67.5E3$.

In 2020 the disparity in H_0 reached 5σ , a disparity caused by ESA-Planck assuming it had measured primordial photons. In ZC ESA-Planck measured the local recent ZME.

ESA-Planck detects 30-857Ghz EMR to measure 160Ghz Blackbody EMR, equated to a cosmic temperature of 2.725K. In ZC Zybertwind plasma colliding with Zybertzone plasma produces Bremsstrahlung radiation i.e. 290Ghz ZMR, which with $\otimes z=0.55$ and Planck $\otimes Z=67.5E3$ has a look back time of 1.94E9y. Supernovae with $z=0.4:0.6$, have look back times of 4.45E9y:5.92E9y, see Table 1.

Table 1. $\otimes Z$ vs look-back time T in years

Look-back time T yrs		$\otimes Z$
Present day	0.0000E+00	64,324
	1.0000E+06	64,326
	1.0000E+07	64,340
	1.0000E+08	64,487
ESA-Planck	1.9437E+09	67,500
$z=0.4$ SNIa	4.4493E+09	71,595
$z=0.6$ SNIa	5.9218E+09	74,000

*Interpreting the measured data for H_0 within Zybert Cosmology: the ESA-Planck data places the average EMR source at 2E3Mpc away ($\otimes z=0.55$) or 1.94E9y ago ($2E3/14.2E3$)*13.8E9 the type 1a supernovae at $z=0.4:0.6$ places the EMR source at 4.45:5.92E9y ago resulting in a linear correlation $\otimes Z=1.634E-6 * T + 64324$*

This data shows there is a linear correlation of measured data, to $R^2=1$, which gives $\otimes \dot{Z}=1.634E-6$ and the present day $\otimes Z=64324$. Table 1 also shows $\otimes Z$ at other look back times calculated using the linear correlation equation.

ESA-Planck detectors cannot detect 290Ghz ZMR further than 4E3Mpc because it is unterZybertshifted to below 30Ghz which is below the lower limit of ESA-Planck detectors.

In deriving $\otimes \dot{Z}=1.634E-6$ from measured data it forms the fourth Test, with $\otimes Z=64324$, $\otimes A'=7.44E-18$ and $\otimes \rho \approx 2E-26$.

11 ZYBERT UNIVERSE

Zybert Cosmology gives no hints of how big the universe is, or how old, or how it came to be. Nor whether mass and light appeared as, or after, empty space appeared.

In ZC there was empty space, then, somewhere, sometime, The Zybert Process (TZP) started creating $n-\bar{n}$ pairs.

The first activation of TZP in the universe feasibly evolved into the first \otimes in the universe, perchance it was $Z(\otimes)$. But, likelier, E? \otimes 's appeared before $Z(\otimes)$, and probably E? after. In ZC there is no data to give any indication.

It is rare for a natural process to be unique, once detected more are found. This applies to stars in galaxies and galaxies in our visible sphere, and by extension, it could also apply to Zybertspheres in the universe. So, as there are stars in galaxies and galaxies in our visible sphere, so there are Zybertspheres in the universe. Giving an elegant uniform spherical symmetry of planets, stars, SNS's, GNS's, \textcircled{Z} cores, and, combinations - planetary, galactic and Zybertspheric systems.

Earth is a speck in our solar system, which is a mere speck in our galaxy, which is just a mere speck in our visible sphere, which is just a mere speck in our \textcircled{Z} , and our \textcircled{Z} is one of E?, and is therefore itself also just a mere speck in the universe.

It is probable that TZP has been, is, and will remain being, continually initiated throughout the universe. One solitary \textcircled{Z} would seem to be a waste of space.

11.1 Zybertsphere Evolution

\textcircled{Z} 's start as one $n\bar{n}$ pair created by TZP usually in an empty region of space, followed by more pairs where $\textcircled{Z}M$ increase is expressed by the Zybert Mass equation.

The neutrons-antineutrons are gravitationally repelled, and in the growing cloud some collide and transform into photons, and vice versa. In the frothing cloud random density variations form clusters of both neutrons and antineutrons. Occasionally, a dominant cluster forms, e.g. of antineutrons, which grows into a dense central antineutron core, which repels neutrons as an enveloping outwardly accelerating spherical neutron cloud. Or vice versa. TZP is active at the matter-antimatter interface at the \textcircled{Z} core surface.

The characteristics of \textcircled{Z} 's are shaped by, the configuration of their evolving embryonic form, random density variations and gravitational attractions/repulsions. Successful \textcircled{Z} 's have configurations which include Zybertzones, and which, usually are conducive to stelliferous evolution.

Generally with spherical Zybertspheres, initially $\textcircled{Z}M^-$ is low and $\textcircled{Z}A^-$ is too low to generate an escape $\textcircled{Z}V$ so that new neutrons are pushed outward by the expanding central core like dust in front of a broom, which lasts for only a short time. As $\textcircled{Z}M$ and $\textcircled{Z}M$ increase, the radial density profile of $\textcircled{Z}M^+$ becomes increasingly weighted nearer the core, because, $\textcircled{Z}M^+$ somewhat overwhelms repulsion by $\textcircled{Z}A^-$ of the $\textcircled{Z}M^-$ core.

\textcircled{Z} cores are the largest antineutron (or neutron) spheres in the universe with enormous immensely powerful magnetic fields, massively bigger than those of GNS's.

The nature of the activity at the surface is different from active stars and NS's, because new $n\bar{n}$ pairs are being created, at an ever increasing rate, forming a dense cloud which is subsequently repelled from the core. There are collisions, gravitational interactions, re-combinations and n 's and \bar{n} 's transform into photons and back again. It is a turbulent region, more turbulent and chaotic than the raging violent storms on star surfaces, and on an immensely massive cosmic scale.

In these environments some neutrons form clusters and others decay into protons-electrons. The half-life of neutrons is $\sim E3s$, and in the turbulent TZP region, in this early stage of

Zybertsphere evolution, random fluctuations create pockets of a density and temperature similar to stars at nuclear ignition, which allows nuclear fusion, and conditions are conducive for baryons fusing to form nuclei of light elements and isotopes, but it is too hot for atoms to form. For comparison, the centre of our sun is at 15E6K and 250E9atm and it has a density of 1.4E3kg/m³.

The repulsion from the core is extremely turbulent with a $\textcircled{Z}V \gg 0$, and reminiscent of mass expelled by our sun which ranges from a continuous stream to giant solar flares. Neutrons closer to the central core in this dense neutron cloud are more strongly repelled and infuse outward into adjacent outer layers of this dense neutron cloud. The increasing $\textcircled{Z}A$ and $\textcircled{Z}V$ have a complex influence on neutrons where newer mix with older in the expanding neutron cloud, creating a complex dynamic evolving radial density profile.

Random neutron clusters form and coalesce into NS's s9.5, which are gravitational foci for the surrounding sea of baryons which later coalesce around them as proto galaxies s9.6.

In the choppy chaotic overwhelming turbulence near TZP, antineutrons are entrapped and coalesce into spheres, spheres of M^- up to -4E36kg or more s9.8.1, and these form voids s9.8.

The giant solar flares of our sun, or even of supernova, are miniscule compared to flares from the core surface of any \textcircled{Z} . These \textcircled{Z} flares are massive and are hurled out into space with similar morphologies to solar flares, forming sheet-like and filament-like and various other types of structures. The larger of such \textcircled{Z} flares evolve into structures over 10E9ly long like the Sloan and Hercules-Corona Borealis Great Walls. $\Lambda\textcircled{Z}$ (local and cosmic) maintains the morphology of such huge structures as originally formed, but, parts closer to $\textcircled{Z}0$ have a greater $\Lambda\textcircled{Z}$ and so, the structure as a whole moves in unison, but not perfect unison, and the morphology changes over time.

The early stage evolution of \textcircled{Z} 's, externally, resembles a starburst firework expanding radially in all directions. The \textcircled{Z} expands like the most common firework, the Peony Shell, as an expanding sphere of baryons. But in \textcircled{Z} 's the expanding baryon distribution is not homogeneous or isotropic. Various baryons of various cluster sizes with a trace of antibaryons all form the embryonic Zybertzone which expands outward, accelerating, and also, later, similar constituents form the Zybertwind.

After, usually billions of years, the receding influence of the expanding Zybertzone reduces to below the contracting influence of local gravity, and the higher density regions of proto galaxies leads to early (super-massive) star formation and subsequent galaxy formation s9.7.

11.2.1 Zybertsphere Variants

Zybertspheres can evolve in many ways. TZP creates neutron-antineutron pairs and gravitational dynamics create random and variable morphologies; spherical \textcircled{Z} 's with an antineutron core enveloped by a neutron cloud, or a neutron core within an antineutron cloud, may not always develop.

If random density fluctuations produce a neutron globule next to an antineutron globule then the two evolve into a dumbbell morphology. No simulations of the evolution of such structures were done. Spherical \mathbb{Z} 's are fixed in space whilst dumbbell \mathbb{Z} 's have two centres of mass moving apart from the creation zone of TZP. If several globules are formed, they may not merge, and different configurations shall result. Possible variations have not been simulated. \mathbb{Z} 's are usually surrounded by empty space and remain stationary in space at a fixed point in space, and do not interact unless they formed close by. \mathbb{Z} 's in 'close' proximity will eventually expand into each other.

There is an infinite range of \mathbb{Z} 's as defined by their final $\mathbb{Z}M$. In ZC simulations, this final mass is represented by Zm in the Zybert Mass Equation. Accurate experimental data will allow Zm of our Zybertsphere to be determined. ZC describes the evolution of \mathbb{Z} 's from birth to eternity. Speculatively, for all Zybertspheres $\Sigma E=0$.

11.2 The Zybert Zybertsphere

Using measured data, analysed within the ZC framework, led to deriving $\mathbb{Z}A'$ and $\mathbb{Z}\dot{Z}$ to define four Tests for evaluating simulations, $\mathbb{Z}Z=64324$, $\mathbb{Z}\dot{Z}=1.634E-6$, $\mathbb{Z}A'=7.4426E-18$ and $\mathbb{Z}\rho=2\pm 1.5E-26$. I thought they might identify the unique Zm for our \mathbb{Z} , but they didn't.

The remarkable characteristic of Zybert Cosmology is that the Zybert Mass Equation always produces mass-time profiles which meet the four Tests for most Zm by using the right Za . To find Za , a few simulations give Za vs $\mathbb{Z}\dot{Z}$ and interpolated to identify the Za giving $\mathbb{Z}\dot{Z}=1.634E-6$. Over the range of Zm $Za=0.048*Zm+22.851$, $R^2=1$ – a Zybert Golden Correlation.

To simulate $Z\mathbb{Z}$, Za was set to produce $\mathbb{Z}\dot{Z}=1.634E-6$ and IC set to produce $\mathbb{Z}A'=7.4426E-18$ at $\mathbb{Z}Z=64324$ while $\mathbb{Z}\rho$ was a simulation result which was usually $2\pm 1.5E-26$, but, the simulation model did not account for neutron collisions and so the radial density profile is less certain.

Graph 1. Evolution of a $\mathbb{Z}T=E0s$ test neutron in our $Zm=32E3$ Zybertsphere vs $\mathbb{Z}T=E0s:E12000s$

Note: x-axis is log scale (i.e. $\log \log \mathbb{Z}T$) and evolution is from $\mathbb{Z}T=E0s$ to $\mathbb{Z}T=E12000s$.

Note: 3a & 4a & 4b are 0 when $\Delta\mathbb{Z}V.N2=0$ (at $\mathbb{Z}T=\sim E7221s$) so are not displayed on the log-log plot.

Legend: 1a. $-\mathbb{Z}M.core$ & $+\mathbb{Z}M.cloud$ 1b. $\mathbb{Z}R.core$ 1c. $\mathbb{Z}V.core$

2a. $\mathbb{Z}R.N2$ 2b. $\mathbb{Z}V.N2$ 2c. $\mathbb{Z}A.N2$

3a. $\mathbb{Z}Z$ 3b. $\mathbb{Z}A'$ 3c. $\mathbb{Z}\rho$

4a. $\Delta\mathbb{Z}Z/\Delta\mathbb{Z}T$ 4b. $\Delta\mathbb{Z}Z/\Delta\mathbb{Z}R$ 4c. $\Delta\mathbb{Z}A'/\Delta\mathbb{Z}T$ 4d. $\Delta\mathbb{Z}A'/\Delta\mathbb{Z}R$

Graph 2. $\text{Z}R$ of core surface and neutrons vs $\text{Z}T=E0s:Now$ and vs $\text{Z}T=E0s:E12000s$

Note: the lower curve is $\text{Z}R_{core}$ and the other curves are $\text{Z}R_{neutrons}$

For $Z_m=0.25E3:512E3$, $\text{Z}Z$, $\text{Z}\dot{Z}$, $\text{Z}A'$, $\text{Z}\rho$, $\Delta\text{Z}A'/\Delta\text{Z}T$ and $\text{Z}T$ all remained constant if using matching Z_a 's and IC 's. Therefore, each Z_m does meet all four Tests, but each Z_m is a different $\text{Z}Z$, in the range $\text{Z}M=E088:E132$, $\text{Z}R=E32:E46$, $\Delta\text{Z}Z/\Delta\text{Z}R=E-28:E-42$ and $\Delta\text{Z}A'/\Delta\text{Z}R=E-49:E-64$.

Several test neutrons were used in all simulations for each $Z_m=0.25E3:512E3$ to find which test neutrons met the Tests, and the M^+ & volume between two test neutrons gave $\text{Z}\rho$. This enabled the Zybertzone to be identified. However, each Z_m produced a Zybertzone which met all four Tests, and in not identifying our unique Z_m I chose $Z_m=32E3$ for now. But, $\text{Z}Z$ anisotropy might help identify our Z_m , s9.2.1.

A $Z_m=32E3|Z_a=1561.5|IC=-17.992|\text{Z}T.N=14.2:14.3$ $\text{Z}Z$ has close matching values for the four Tests. Simulations are imprecise, being based on derived estimates for $\text{Z}\dot{Z}$ and $\text{Z}A'$. $\text{Z}Z$ vs $\text{Z}T$ for $Z_m=0.25E3:512E3$ are identical for $\text{Z}T>E5s$, $\text{Z}Z=-0.9986*\text{Z}T+15.389$, $R^2=1$. For $\text{Z}Z$, at $\text{Z}T=39.81E9y$, $\text{Z}Z=74700$ (74000 in Table1) at $T=5.92E9y$ look back time, $\text{Z}Z=66900$ (67500 in Table1) at $T=1.94E9y$ ESA-Planck and $\text{Z}Z=63656$ (64324 in Table 1) at $T=0$. So, the age of our Z is $\text{Z}ZT=39.81E9y$ and our visible sphere is made from neutrons created at $\text{Z}ZT=E14.2:E14.3s$ i.e. $\text{Z}ZT=5E6:6E6y$.

Better experimental data and geometry, better simulation resolution and refinement of the model for the radial density profile will give results with a better fit. The radial density profile in particular must be better modelled to produce a more accurate $\text{Z}\rho$ and to help locate our radial position in our Z , but such simulations need more than just a desktop PC.

$IC=-17.992$ means ~ 0.9999999999999999 of $\text{Z}M^+$ is within the test neutron $\text{Z}R$, and $E-17.992*\text{Z}M^+$ is outside, so the effective mass at $\text{Z}Z0$ is $E-17.992*\text{Z}M^-$. In this way IC represents the weighting of $\text{Z}M^+$ nearer the core, reducing the effective $\text{Z}M^-$ and hence $\text{Z}A$, to result in the derived $\text{Z}A'$.

The refined simulation model with the established design parameters (and which meet the four Tests) can now provide a detailed history of the evolution of our Zybertsphere. The evolution of our Zybertsphere is fascinating, Graph 1, though, while a full history cannot be given here some aspects can be.

11.2.1 In the Beginning

39.81E9y ago, E45.73m from earth, in the direction of the higher $\text{Z}z$ in the ZME, where cosmic rays originate, there was empty space. Then TZP initiated, creating neutron-antineutron pairs, increasingly, as expressed by the Zybert Mass Equation. The cloud happened to evolve having a spherical form with a dense core of antineutrons enveloped by a cloud of neutrons.

The evolution of our Zybertsphere, from origin up to now, followed the traditional evolutionary path as described above.

One aspect of the evolution of Zybertspheres which cannot be depicted in Graph 1 is the changing radial density profile. Current simulations do not explore the complex intermingling of older and newer neutrons. The nature of the changing radial density profile will help refine the evolution of $\text{Z}s'$ and the radial regions which are stelliferous and our radial position.

11.2.2 Epoch E0s:E5.5s

$\text{Z}A^-$ and $\text{Z}V$ are small and the expanding surface of the core pushes newly created neutrons ahead of it like dust in front of a broom creating a dense spherical annulus of neutrons, which generally forms the embryonic Zybertzone. Newly created neutrons merge with the inner surface of this annulus, thus adding to and enlarging the Zybertzone. Early in this phase, density variations create neutron clusters which later evolve into NS 's, s9.6.

11.2.3 Epoch E5.5s:E10s

Z^- repels this zone and ever more newly created neutrons follow, and merge with this zone at the inner surface and mingle with it, some adding to the neutron clusters which are now evolving into NS's. The density is lowest at the outer surface and higher toward Z^0 , but overall is decreasing as this zone expands. Neutrons decay into protons-electrons and in some pockets nuclei form, not atoms. Radial expansion is accelerating with the ever increasing Z^M . A small Λ^{local} of the evolving NS's attracts local surrounding baryons which are generally receding due to the initial repulsive Z^- , represented by Z . These baryons, surrounding the NS's, will later collapse under Λ^{local} to form proto galaxies s9.7.

11.2.4 Epoch E10s:E18.098s

New neutrons, decayed into protons-electrons, overtake us as Cosmic Rays and are accelerated past the baryon outer surface of the Zybertzone, which is expanding, and thus merge with the outer surface, e.g. neutrons created at $\text{Z}^T \approx E14.5s$ have overtaken us and just now, $\text{Z}^T \approx E18.098s$, are merging with the outer surface of the expanding Zybertzone, Graph 2a.

As the Zybertzone expands, Z and ρ fall, increasingly, neutrons transform into protons-electrons and by $\text{Z}^T \approx 15E9y$ $\text{Z} \approx E5.1$ and $\rho \approx E-24.4$ and for an $M = 6E42$ within $R = 3E22$ (our galaxy $R \approx 60$) V reaches 0, and baryons start collapsing to form proto galaxies. By $\text{Z}^T \approx 20E9y$ some stars are born.

Currently, for Z , $\text{Z}^T = 39.81E9y$ and $\text{Z}^M = E130.33kg$ and yet Z^M is only $E-31872$ of its final Z^M to be reached at $\text{Z}^T \approx E6020s$ i.e. $\approx E6013y$, or, 'one' then 'trillion' 501 times then 'years'.

Core $\text{Z}^R = E37.36m$ ($E-19.68\%$ of the Z^0 radius) and the core surface outward $\text{Z}^V = E19.73m/s$.

The Zybertzone inner surface is $E45.7270m$ from Z^0 and the outer is $E45.7844m$ so the Zybertzone is $E44.8776m$ wide, but is only 0.0000000005% of the Z^0 radius, and yet it could fit $8.57E17$ of our visible spheres, radially.

Between the core and Zybertzone are new neutrons, which comprise $\sim 99.9999999999999999\%$ of all neutrons, and ρ is $\sim E9$ near the core and $\sim E-26$ in the Zybertzone. Most of the remaining neutrons form the Zybertzone, with no delineation between the two, it being a gradual density change where the Zybertzone $\rho \approx E-26$, and higher inward and lower outward, but may still be stelliferous. In Z^0 baryons forming our sector of the Zybertzone, and our visible sphere, were created during $\text{Z}^T = E14.2:E14.3s$ i.e. $\text{Z}^T = 5E6:6E6y$. Currently, for earth, $\text{Z}^R = E45.78$, $\text{Z}^V = E28.02$ and $\text{Z}^A = E10.53$.

To assess our radial position within our Zybertzone will need simulations to obtain a precise radial density profile. A profile formed by a complex evolution of motion and mixing of neutrons where ρ is $\sim E9$ near the core and falls to 0 at R_0 .

In our Z , TZP is currently creating neutrons at $E113.2kg/s$. The decayed and combined & re-combined (anti)neutrons are accelerated outward as Zybertwind, but the many collisions in traversing the Zybertzone merge some within the Zybertzone

before reaching us, and the rest pass us as Cosmic Rays and some of those exit the outer Zybertsphere surface.

In Zybertwind, two or more bound neutrons do not decay and those which collide with nuclei, especially nuclei of or heavier than iron, could be captured creating heavier elements.

Internal Z structure is like earth or our sun, and perhaps others; a small dense central core with a huge less dense shell covered by a thin atmosphere, which on earth supports life and in Z 's support stars, and above this atmosphere is virtually empty space. With Z 's, the outer zone past the Zybertzone has an average $\rho \approx E-65.39kg/m^3$; $\sim E-26$ near the Zybertzone down to 0 at the Z outer edge, and into totally empty space.

Currently new neutrons are subjected to $\text{Z}^A = \sim E45$ and would reach us in a few seconds without collisions, but take much longer and are slowed by collisions and Bremsstrahlung radiation before reaching the Zybertzone and then passing us as Cosmic Rays or UHECR's.

11.2.5 Epoch E18.098s:E2600s

New neutrons pass through and out of the Zybertzone but by $\text{Z}^T \approx E5000s$ the Zybertzone has expanded so its outer surface reaches the E2600s neutrons, Graph 2b, and the E18:E2600 neutrons merge with the outer Zybertzone and also expand it. But, many neutrons are trapped within the Zybertzone (as decayed neutrons / Cosmic Rays) before they can reach its outer surface, so further mixing older and newer neutrons.

It is seen that the Zybertzone will continue to grow in mass and volume up to E2600s, but simulations have not been done to calculate ρ of this newer younger Zybertzone region and so it is unknown how much of it will be stelliferous.

11.2.6 Epoch E2600s:E12000+s

At $\geq E2600s$, new neutrons passing through the Zybertzone do not merge with the outer Zybertzone as earlier neutrons did, but instead, they create laminar layers outside the Zybertzone on its outer surface, Graph 2b. All neutrons created after E2600s add layers onto older layers forming a **multilayered laminar zone** on the Zybertzone outer surface. This laminar zone is a separate zone to the Zybertzone, a zone which is not likely to be stelliferous. As with earlier neutrons, some are trapped in the Zybertzone before reaching its outer surface thus adding to the mass of the Zybertzone, but it is unlikely this extra mass will be enough for new star formation.

Laminar layers are added up to $\text{Z}^T \approx E5600s$, just as our Z has reached its maximum mass and neutron creation dwindles. The growth of our Z is ending. Its destiny has been fulfilled.

12 OBSERVATIONS

Zybert Gravity, Zybert Light and Zybert Time always behave the same everywhere, from the quantum scale of a $9.1E-31kg$ electron to the cosmic scale of an $E1000kg$ antineutron sphere, at the surface or at $E1000m$ away. Zybert light is dynamic and Zybert Time is universal and absolute.

The results from Zybert Cosmology, derive in part, from measured data, which produces inaccuracies. Cosmological data is often based on a homogeneous and isotropic universe, and this filter permeates from the design of experiments to the analysis and interpretation of results. This creates inaccuracies in ZC because \mathbb{Z} 's are not isotropic or homogeneous.

Since \mathbb{Z} 's are not isotropic or homogeneous, location and direction are crucial, hence a Zybertsphere Coordinate System (ZCS) is crucial. Fortuitously the ultimate fundamental axis does exist in all visible spheres, the Axis of Zybert $\mathbb{t}(\mathbb{Z})$. The primary axis of the ZCS, the z-axis, is also the primary \mathbb{Z} axis, the Axis of Zybert. \mathbb{Z} geometry is simplified with the ZCS since many phenomena are caused by $\Lambda(\mathbb{Z})$ which is referenced to the Axis of Zybert. 0,0,0 of the ZCS is $\mathbb{Z}0$.

This anisotropy, and $\Lambda(\mathbb{Z})$, causes a curvature in all motion, so, observed cosmic entities are not where they appear to be. For example, Hyades is centred at $y=0$, $s6.3.3$, but $\mathbb{Z}\theta$.cosmic for $\theta(\mathbb{Z})=1^\circ$ gives its apparent position as $y=-4.65614E17$ and during an eclipse as $y=-4.65608E17$. In ZC the 'non-deflected reference light' does not indicate the true source position.

In ZC any photons created in $Z(\mathbb{Z})$ during the creation of the $n-\bar{n}$ pairs which form our visible sphere, if currently visible in our visible sphere, are of such low number and low intensity compared with the ZME as to be unobservable.

In ZC, for a sufficiently high \hat{c} , long fixed length EMR would be perceived as just a blip.

Although $\mathbb{Z}Z$ can be considered the counterpart of H_0 , H_0 is taken as the age of the universe, but $\mathbb{Z}Z$ is unrelated to age, though, $\mathbb{Z}Z$ vs $\mathbb{Z}T$ is log-log linear with $R^2=1$.

Although $\mathbb{Z}Z$ vs $\mathbb{Z}T$ is log-log linear for $\mathbb{Z}T=1s$ neutrons, for later neutrons $\mathbb{Z}Z$ starts with $\mathbb{Z}Z$ of the core surface and once repelled from the core and accelerated to outside of the outer baryon surface of the \mathbb{Z} where $\mathbb{Z}A=0$ $\mathbb{Z}Z\approx 0$, but then as the Zybertzone expands into these baryons $\mathbb{Z}Z$ increases to the same as that of the baryons within the Zybertzone.

13 CONCLUSIONS

An earth-centric cosmology with epicycles was proposed by Apollonius of Perga in the 3rd century BC. It convincingly explained planetary orbits and was spectacularly successful, but, a long list of anomalous or inexplicable cosmological observations, implied it was flawed, most probably terminally, yet it remained influential until Copernican Helio-centrism in 1543 resolved the anomalies and simplified the complexity.

The Standard Model of Cosmology was developed over decades, based on observations, and it convincingly explains the evolution of the universe and it is spectacularly successful, but, a long list of anomalous or inexplicable cosmological observations, imply it is flawed, perhaps terminally. As new data emerged, of higher quality and accuracy, more anomalies were identified or verified. Most recently, perhaps the biggest, is the Hubble crisis now at 5σ where new physics is advocated. Yet it still remains influential, but now, Zybert Cosmology in 2021 resolves the anomalies and simplifies the complexity.

Standard gravitational analyses applied to Zybertspheres, within Zybert Cosmology and based on a few bold postulates, explain such diverse phenomena as the precession of orbits, bending of light, the origin of voids and supermassive entities, baryonic asymmetry, accelerated expansion, GPS inaccuracy, flyby velocity gains, constant rotational velocity of galaxies, UHECR's, the increasing angular size of galaxies, background microwaves and resolves the 5σ Hubble Crisis and a lot more.

For decades Cosmology has been focused on mathematics. This inevitably led to anomalies. ZC focusses on Physics and conceptual physical models, to give breathtakingly audacious ultra-radical bold new visions of the physical universe. New paradigms. A new perception of profound insight revealing a revolutionary realisation of the most ingenious model of the physical universe ever imagined. In its boldness and audacity, past anomalies are simply inherent features native to \mathbb{Z} 's. The precession of Mercury can be analysed with Classical Physics. GPS inaccuracies are explained by the relative speed of light, as are other anomalies, and analysed with Classical Physics.

ZC is the most radical conception of the universe ever. The most radical, even heretical, alternative to all cosmologies of recent centuries. A gigantic revolutionary leap of imagination in visualising the Cosmos, far beyond anything ever imagined. Yet, it does not beggar belief, has no inherent contradictions, is not counter-intuitive, explains cosmological phenomena, is consistent with and replicates measured cosmological data, resolves the 40+ anomalies as just inherent features of \mathbb{Z} 's and introduces no new anomalies, has no physical or mathematical abnormalities like singularities, harmonizes Hubble values, explains 100% of the universe without relying on mysterious particles or fields, conforms to Classical & Quantum Physics, and, parameters are plainly interrelated and highly correlated.

Zybert Cosmology is a new understanding of the Cosmos. ZC is so radically different to any previous cosmology, is such a totally new paradigm, that I hope this renaissance inspires gifted Cosmologists and Astrophysicists and Astronomers to unshackle their preconceptions and unleash their full innate powers of imagination. Scientific imaginations unhindered by untenable assumptions and outmoded beliefs. To go where no science has gone before. Science as more science than fiction. To do actual science, not dream up euphemisms or illusions. All the while exploiting Mathematics as an analytical tool to evaluate conceptual physical models and not rely on or expect Mathematics to do Physics. To liberate their deepest creative conceptualisations of reality. To stand apart. Break the mould. The lone wolf out front leading the pack. The solitary genius. The one of superior intellect. The chosen one who stands alone on a higher plane above mere mortals closer to the Gods!

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REFERENCES

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